

iJERResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, March- 2023 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10104648

INNS IN CALDAS NOVAS (GO): MANAGEMENT AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH THE ENVIRONMENT FROM 2015 TO 2020

AUTHORS

Ronaldo do Nascimento Carvalho (dr.ronaldocarvalho@gmail.com); Joana D'arc Bardella Castro (joanabardellacastro@gmail.com); Carine do Santos Ribeiro (carineribeiro@hotmail.com)

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the management and relationship with the environment, in the years 2015 to 2020, of hostels in Caldas Novas, a municipality in the state of Goiás, which has a very high economic development, driven by the growth of the state's large urban centers.